

LIQUID RENEWABLE ENERGY CARRIERS FROM
CAPTURED CARBON EMISSIONS

DELIVERABLE D1.4

Report detailing the RRI applied in CAPTUS and
the overall status of the project.

PROJECT NO:
101118265

PROJECT ACRONYM:
CAPTUS

PROJECT TITLE:
Demonstrating energy intensive industry-
integrated solutions to produce liquid renewable
energy carriers from CAPTURED carbon emissionS

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DISCLAIMER FOR METHODOLOGY

This project has used a standard methodology already developed in the eFORT project (grant agreement number: 101075665), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the grant agreement conditions for CAPTUS (grant agreement number: 101118265).

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public – fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D1.4 RRI First Report aims to introduce the initial approach to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) within the CAPTUS project.

The document begins by briefly presenting the project and its objectives. After that, the report provides a concise overview of what is RRI, which are the different axis and which of them are currently applicable in this first approach.

RRI will be evaluated at different stages of the project. D1.4 presents the first review, which will be reviewed in M30 and M48 with deliverables D1.6 and D1.9, respectively.

TABLE OF CONTENT

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES	II
DISCLAIMER FOR METHODOLOGY	II
1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES	1
1.1 CAPTUS PROJECT	1
1.2 OBJECITVE AND SCOPE	1
2 BASICS OF RRI	2
2.1 THEMES OF RRI.....	2
2.1.1 ETHICS.....	3
2.1.2 OPEN ACCESS.....	4
2.1.3 PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT	5
2.1.4 GOVERNANCE	6
2.1.5 SCIENCE EDUCATION.....	6
2.1.6 GENDER Equality.....	7
2.2 SOME SOURCES OF INFORMATION	8
3 CONCLUSION.....	8
4 BIBLIOGRAPHY	9

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Promote learning in the scope of the CAPTUS project (Brandt M. et al., 2022)7

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. RRI axis reproduced from (RRI toolkit, 2023)2
Figure 2. Public Engagement relevancy per key actor (RRI toolkit, 2023).....5

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CCU	Carbon Capture and Utilization
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EII	Energy Intensive Industry
RE	Renewable Energy
REC	Renewable Energy Carriers
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work package
WT	Work task

1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

1.1 CAPTUS PROJECT

The major challenge faced by Energy intensive industries (EII) is the reduction of carbon emissions while remaining competitive in accordance with the ambitious EU climate policies. In this context, Carbon Capture and Utilization (CCU) technologies, powered by renewable energy (RE), will play a key role in preventing further carbon release into the atmosphere while simultaneously obtaining valuable products from it. The CAPTUS project aims to transform CO₂ derived from EII operations into a valuable resource through the industrial demonstration of three promising CCU technologies. These technologies will valorize CO₂ captured from cement, steel and chemical plants into different Renewable Energy Carriers (REC). The process involves the integration of surplus RE, contributing to a more efficient and sustainable transition, with detailed analyses on safety, environmental, societal, and business aspects.

1.2 OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE

The key objective of this project is to demonstrate sustainable, cost-effective, and scalable pathways to produce high-added value energy carriers in EIIs by valorizing industrial carbon emissions and integrating renewable electricity surplus. To this end, different innovative solutions involving CO₂ capture and conversion technologies will be developed and implemented in three real demonstration sites at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7 (cement, steel, and chemical plant), together with a detailed consideration on safety, environmental, societal and business aspects.

Furthermore, the specific objectives related to this project include:

1. To develop and validate bespoke CO₂ capture units capable of conditioning the emitted industrial flue gases for their subsequent conversion into high-value RECs.
2. To develop and validate innovative technologies for the conversion of CO₂ into valuable liquid RECs by sustainable and efficient processes.
3. To develop robust simulation and modelling tools that facilitate the design, optimization and upscaling of CCU technologies in industrial scenarios, identifying and overcoming technical barriers and strongly considering the hybridization with renewable electricity surplus.
4. To validate the quality of the produced RECs and the feasibility of their upgrading into cleaner and more sustainable fuels that allow carbon footprint and economic savings in the EII sector.
5. To establish a roadmap for the implementation of CAPTUS solutions in other industrial realities, tackling technical and non-technical (i.e., regulatory and standardisation) barriers.
6. To assure a successful exploitation and dissemination of the project, through a strategic and business-oriented commercialization plan, dedicated business models and key stakeholders' engagement.

2 BASICS OF RRI

RRI is an approach that considers the societal expectations and the implications that the Research and Innovation may have. One definition of RRI is provided by René Von Schomberg in 2011 “Responsible Research and Innovation is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (in order to allow a proper embedding of scientific and technological advances in our society)”. From this statement we can conclude the objective of this approach which is to balance the commercial goals of the research with a wider wellbeing respecting the general stakeholders’ expectations. This approach has been recently promoted by the European Union’s Framework Programs towards scientific research and technological development processes.

Different institutions are related with RRI depending on their profile. From policymakers to business and civil society organizations, there are five interest groups identified which could be affected by the project research and should be considered under the umbrella of RRI. CAPTUS outcomes should (i) be interoperable, (ii) have an international approach and (iii) ensure the interdisciplinary.

2.1 THEMES OF RRI

This deliverable will be based on the European Commission (EC) orientations which aims to cover the RRI from six axis or dimensions presented in Figure 1:

Figure 1. RRI axis reproduced from (RRI toolkit, 2023)

Every aspect of the Responsible Research Innovation approach needs a series of conditions to achieve the desired outcomes. Those conditions should be promoted by the whole consortium during the project developments so as to ensure the proper implementation of RRI in CAPTUS. The required conditions have been greatly discussed and analyzed in a great number of articles but the

project New Horizon in its deliverable “Ensuring Societal Readiness, a thinking tool” (New Horizon, 2017) has found 4 common conditions in the literature:

1. **Anticipation** is a reflection exercise to understand the context and find out possible consequences from the research. Through this anticipation, researchers can depict the associated risks and prepare contingency plans during the research with the common question “What if...?”.
2. **Reflexivity** is about rethinking and reflecting on the processes already established in order to know if they still fit for purpose or if pivoting is needed. Motivations, assumptions and commitments should be common for all participants and valuable for the whole society.
3. **Inclusion** of relevant stakeholders from the beginning of the project following a constant communication to ensure achieving the desired impact. The exchange of information and opinions can bring new ideas and directions for the developments.
4. **Responsiveness** to the previous conditions to ensure the proper implementation of Responsible Research Innovation during the project. To achieve a proper responsiveness partners should ensure the applicability of their experience and lessons learned along the project.

Only some of the RRI dimensions are studied deeply in this deliverable. Future versions may consider adding information and measures to the other policies. It is important to state that at the current stage of the project, only some of them will be explored. This living approach will be continued within the project.

2.1.1 ETHICS

Ethics plays an integral part of research from beginning to end, and ethical compliance is seen as pivotal to achieve research excellence. The CAPTUS consortium will follow good research practices based on the four cornerstone principles of research integrity (ALLEA, 2023):

1. **Reliability** in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources.
2. **Honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way.
3. **Respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment.
4. **Accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organization, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impact.

From those principles, CAPTUS has achieved a research environment capable of founding a culture of research integrity, mutual respect among participants and avoiding misconduct. Authors agree on the acknowledgement, are transparent and request approval and review from the consortium before publishing. Furthermore, the project counts with a well-balanced participation with different interdisciplinary expertise and previous experience which ensures a research close to the state-of-the-art and the use of relevant and efficient research procedures.

Even though, CAPTUS does not deal with work in ethical-compromised areas as the investigation of human embryos, humans, or animals, the researchers working in the project recognize and weight potential harms and risks for which contingency and mitigation plans have been defined.

The practices and procedures for the data management have been detailed in the D1.2 “Data Management Plan” in which can be found a summary of the data that will be used, the FAIR principles, allocation of resources, data security and ethics. Moreover, the personal data used within the frame of the project will follow the EU regulations regarding General Data Protection Regulation, to ensure that the data is protected accordingly.

To conclude, the three types of misconduct behavior in proposing, performing or reviewing research have been presented to the partners in order to avoid further violation of the good research practices that governs the CAPTUS project as stated in The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity:

1. **Fabrication** is making up data or results and recording them as if they were real.
2. **Falsification** is manipulating research materials, equipment, images, or processes, or changing, omitting, or suppressing data or results without justification.
3. **Plagiarism** is using other people’s work or ideas without giving proper credit to the original source.

2.1.2 OPEN ACCESS

Open Access refers to “the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable.” (European Commission 2019). The CAPTUS project developments as any other scientific research needs to verify its data while sharing its results with the scientific community. This open research context ensures the verification of research by the whole community, avoiding possible duplications. The investigations carried out during the project will follow the principle “*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*”. Sensitive information will not be disclosed outside of the consortium to protect the developments while considering exploitation and dissemination needs. However, the consortium agreed during its first year to follow the FAIR principles to ensure that the data can be reproduced, shared, and used by external entities when the confidentiality needs potentially disappear.

Public reports, and public information will be presented on the project webpage (<https://captusproject.eu/>) and in the project ZENODO’s community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/captus?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>). Furthermore, project information will be shared through newsletters, videos, leaflets, and partner participation in events.

CAPTUS also aims to exchange information with several stakeholders. The project has already participated in different conferences such as the European Symposium on Computer Aided Process Engineering, International Symposium on Process Systems Engineering, 27th International Congress of Chemical and Process Engineering CHISA 2024, and the Carbon Capture Summit Europe 2024, among others. Nonetheless, CAPTUS will continue to promote partner participation in different events with general stakeholders, from open visits to demos to participation in specific forums. These actions will be ensured to provide society with public information from the project. Specific events are not defined at the current stage of the project and tentative forums will be investigated in the coming months. All the previous information will be published in future deliverables of the WP8 “Dissemination and Communication”.

2.1.3 PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

Public engagement is considered one of the pillar of Responsible Research Innovation. The involvement of general public and target audience is of paramount importance for contributing to the societal well-being and sustainability, something that CAPTUS has acknowledged from the very beginning. Through public engagement, the CAPTUS project aims to foster transparency, trust, and accountability through the dissemination of the project results. During this section, we will explain the public engagement roadmap of the CAPTUS project, from its purpose to the measurement of the value created. Nonetheless, this study will be from a general perspective as there is a specific workpage responsible for public engagement: WP8. All the CAPTUS consortium needs to understand and keep in mind the purpose of the public engagement, the deliverables and outcomes, the target stakeholders, similar activities already made by other bodies, and the potential barriers that could be encountered during the engagement.

Before analysing the public engagement roadmap of the CAPTUS project, the consortium needs to clearly understand the purpose of the project. CAPTUS seeks to demonstrate sustainable and cost-effective pathways to produce high-added value Renewable Energy Carriers in Energy Intensive Industries by valorising industrial carbon emissions and integrating renewable electricity surplus. With that in mind, the project has analysed the five key actors identified in RRI, considering the benefits of engaging them as depicted in Figure 2:

Figure 2. Public Engagement relevancy per key actor (RRI toolkit, 2023)

These five key actors have been analysed considering the interest in the project, the benefits CAPTUS could provide, and the support of the exploitation of results. The result has been a preliminary definition of the stakeholders and target audience on which the project wants to focus the engagement activities: energy-intensive industries and technology providers, RES promoters and electric system operators, industry and economic stakeholders, policymakers and public bodies, technical experts and scientific community and civil society, general public, NGOs, initiatives and projects.

Furthermore, the success of the project relies on whether or not the goals are achieved, and for that, the definition of the project results and outcomes is essential. The assessment of these results and outcomes will be carried out in the WP7 "Exploitation and Business Models", specifically in the task related to the IPR review and exploitation strategy T7.2.

Another important first step to consider is the analysis of previous public engagement efforts from similar national, regional, or international projects, which be conducted in the WP8, leveraging synergies with other projects and initiatives.

To conclude, CAPTUS will disseminate the project following three communication models: the traditional linear model of communication focused on the general public and using mainly social media, the interactive model in which partners expect feedback from the audience with the participation in events and fairs face-to-face and online, and the transactional in which communicators exchange information, shaping their opinions through internal and external workshops.

2.1.4 GOVERNANCE

Strong and robust governance structures that promote RRI help to reduce potential misunderstanding, conflicts, and the need for unforeseen procedures. The project Res-AGorA developed a series of guidelines to ensure RRI governance and the CAPTUS project focuses its governance on those principles and requirements for proper implementation. The project's governance has been defined considering each of the activities carried out during the project. Each activity or task has a partner responsible for its development, also known as the Task Leader. The set of tasks within a topic forms a work package, which also has an appointed partner responsible. This structure ensures the quality of interactions, as participants in a topic can maintain fluid communication with their leader, who is also responsible for building trust, collecting data and organizing dialogue among participants. Nonetheless, this structure cannot be RRI-oriented without a decision-making procedure capable of engaging the relevant stakeholders participating or not in the project and confronting, synthesizing, and compromising to achieve relevant results for society. This structure is depicted in the deliverable D1.1 (CAPTUS project, 2023), which also describes the two main governance bodies (General assembly and Steering Committee) and the role of each participant. These governance bodies oversee the work packages and tasks considering the knowledge and decision of the whole consortium. Furthermore, the project's structured approach fosters a supportive environment in which partners can share their knowledge and capacities, promoting transparency and tolerance.

2.1.5 SCIENCE EDUCATION

Science education aims to contribute to innovative problem-solving and critical thinking in the society, enhancing citizens's ability to participate in research and innovation processes. This education will ensure interdisciplinary approaches in the future and greater stakeholders' involvement, making the society more resilient and innovative. It should be based on the RRI principles making it accessible and understandable for any public. Furthermore, it should be adapted depending on the target audience, using plain language for non-experts and identifying the background and interests of experts. Nonetheless, learning is motivated by engagement, and activities should be conducted in environments where people feel comfortable, free to experiment, and without fear. The Horizon Europe program facilitates the creation of a social environment where partners can connect with others who share the same interest and purposes, motivating them to learn through experience, conversation, sharing and collaboration. The CAPTUS project also aims

to create different learning opportunities, which are detailed in Table 1

Table 1. Promote learning in the scope of the CAPTUS project (Brandt M. et al., 2022)

Opportunity	Implementation	Considerations to improve learning when implementing in context of the project
Co-Design of the project	Involve participants in developing research questions, study design, data analysis and/or communication	Implementation of workshops to share lessons learnt and new considerations for the project execution
Communicating with participants	use uni - directional communication (e.g. emails, social media, website, field guides) as well as dialogue /social interactions (e.g. online, or in person at formal or informal meetings)	Acknowledge participants contributions, refer participants to other projects, make content more accessible, use clear language...
Promoting peer-to-peer communication	use narrative story telling by participants (e.g. photo diaries), online communication (e.g. social media, blogs), formal and informal meetings	encourage more advanced participants to teach beginners, support critical thinking...
Clustering activities	Contact with sister projects	Contact a major number of projects from different calls (regional, national and international), run joint communication activities and workshops

2.1.6 GENDER EQUALITY

Achieving Gender Equality is a long process and requires a strategic and systematic approach. In RRI, Gender Equality seeks to offer equal opportunities, participation and outcomes for all genders. This equality is reached when: (1) women and men are equally represented in all disciplines and at all hierarchical levels, (2) gendered barriers are abolished so that women and men can develop their potential equally, and (3) when the gender dimension is considered in all research and innovation activities” (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2018) .

CAPTUS partners are committed to foster gender equality following the commitment in Horizon Europe program (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021). This commitment aims to have more women participating in research and innovation programs and to better integrate the gender dimension in the research and innovation projects. The gender perspective will be studied throughout the lifetime of the project from two different perspectives:

- The technologies developed must, to the greatest extent possible, consider the

gender dimension and to avoid any potential discrimination.

- The CAPTUS project partners will strive to achieve gender-balanced teams to the extent possible.

Thus, the KPIs for gender Equality within the effort project will include:

- Percentage of females over the total workforce of the project
- Number of entities with a Gender Equity Plan

2.2 SOME SOURCES OF INFORMATION

This section aims to provide to the partners with sources of information regarding RRI that should be used during the lifetime of the project, to consider this holistic approach when research.

RRI tools: [Home Page - RRI Tools \(rri-tools.eu\)](https://rri-tools.eu/)

“A practical Guide to Responsible Research and Innovation: Key lessons from RRI tools”
From RRI project:

[RRI+Tools.+A+practical+guide+to+Responsible+Research+and+Innovation.+Key+Lessons+from+RRI+Tools \(rri-tools.eu\)](https://rri-tools.eu/)

Self-reflecting tool: [Self-Reflection Tool - RRI Tools \(rri-tools.eu\)](https://rri-tools.eu/)

Putting Responsible Research and Innovation into Practice [Putting Responsible Research and Innovation into Practice: A Multi-Stakeholder Approach | SpringerLink](https://www.springerlink.com/)

Enacting RRI in Europe course: [RRI - Aalborg University \(aau.dk\)](https://www.aau.dk/)

The Societal Readiness Thinking Tool: <https://thinkingtool.eu/>

3 CONCLUSION

The current report establishes the foundation for integrating RRI principles within the CAPTUS project. With this groundwork, the project will track how RRI best practices are implemented throughout its duration. Subsequent efforts will be tracked and evaluated during project execution.

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